

Interaction of Charcoal and Bromine in Aqueous Solution

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The nature of the reaction between charcoal and bromine in aqueous solution depends to a large extent on the nature of the charcoal surface as influenced by its associated oxygen. When oxygen, capable of evolving carbon dioxide on high-temperature evacuation, is present, the reaction involves hydrolysis of bromine and chemisorption of an equivalent amount of oxygen. When this form of oxygen is absent, the reaction involves 'fixation' of an appreciable amount of bromine, probably at some unsaturated sites, there being little or no hydrolysis. The amount of bromine fixed is seen to be a definite quantity for a given sample of charcoal. The heat evolved during the process is quite close to the heat of addition of bromine in ethylenic double bond as reported in literature.

It appears from the literature that although the interaction of charcoal and carbon blacks with chlorine as well as iodine in aqueous solution has been studied by several workers (Behrman and Gustafson, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1935, *27*, 426; Watson and Parkinson, *ibid.*, 1955, *47*, 1053; Smith *et al.*, 1941, *33*, 1303; Puri *et al.*; this *Journal*, 1960, *37*, 471, 401; Razouk and Shimmi, *A'in. Sham. Sci. Bull.*, 1957, No. 2, 203; King, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 489) and different mechanisms of the processes involved have been suggested, the interaction with bromine under similar conditions has not received as much attention. The present work was therefore undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two samples of charcoal, prepared by carbonisation of recrystallised cane sugar (by pure sulphuric acid followed by exhaustive washings with hot distilled water) and coconut shell charcoal (by burning small pieces at 350° in a limited supply of air), were used in these investigations. Sugar charcoal was almost free of ash; the other sample was extracted with hydrofluoric acid to lower the ash content to about 0.2%. These samples, referred to as 'original samples' in the text, were used as such as well as after evacuating at 750° and 1100°. The amount of combined oxygen as well as its disposition in each sample was estimated by evacuating 2 g. portion at 1200° in a resistance tube furnace, collecting water in calcium chloride tubes, and analysing the rest of the gases evolved in an Orsat-Lunge gas analysis apparatus in the usual way. The results are shown in Table I. It is seen that the original samples contain considerable amounts of chemisorbed oxygen which is evolved as carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, and water. The samples degassed at 750° contain oxygen capable of evolving carbon monoxide and water only, but those degassed at 1100° do not contain any oxygen at all.

Aqueous solutions of bromine in potassium bromide of concentrations varying from 0.025 to 0.130*N* were used.

Procedure.—One g. portions of charcoal were mixed with 250 c.c. of bromine solution. The suspensions were shaken mechanically in half-pound stoppered bottles, wrapped in thick black papers, for different intervals of time, after which an aliquot of the supernatant liquid was examined for unchanged bromine and hydrobromic acid formed, if any, by the usual analytical methods.

Thermal Effect.—The heat evolved during the interaction of 750° and 1100° evacuated sugar charcoal with bromine water was determined by the calorimetric technique described earlier (Puri *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, 82, 756). The charcoal sample (5 g.), suspended in CO₂-free water (25 c.c.) to eliminate immersionsal thermal effects, was immersed in bromine water (200 c.c.) of increasing concentration, contained in the calorimeter, with all necessary precautions. The rise in temperature was noted in the usual way after every 2 minutes till the rate of further rise of temperature became extremely slow. This usually required a little more than an hour. The charcoal was then taken out, washed exhaustively with water, and the solution analysed for its bromine content.

TABLE I

Combined oxygen evolved as oxides of carbon and water on evacuating different samples of sugar and coconut shell charcoals at 1200°.

Description of the sample.	Oxygen (g./100 g.) evolved as			Total combined oxygen (g./100 g.).
	CO ₂ .	CO.	H ₂ O.	
	Sugar charcoal.			
Original	10.77	8.05	11.11	29.93
Degassed at 750°	Nil	5.54	5.73	11.27
Degassed at 1100°	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
	Coconut shell charcoal.			
Original	5.07	6.22	6.86	18.15
Degassed at 750°	Nil	4.34	5.39	9.72
Degassed at 1100°	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil

TABLE II

Interaction of the original samples of sugar and coconut shell charcoals with bromine water.
Amount of bromine added to 1 g. charcoal=250 c.c. of 0.075*N* (18.75 m.e.).

Analysis of bromine water (in m.e.) after shaking for different intervals of time.

Time of shaking.	Bromine unchanged.	HBr formed.	Total amount of Br ₂ and HBr.	%Bromine converted to HBr.	Bromine unchanged.	HBr formed.	Total amount of Br ₂ and HBr.	%Bromine converted to HBr.
	Sugar charcoal (original).				Coconut shell charcoal (original).			
2 hrs.	14.29	4.46	18.75	23.78	16.16	2.56	18.72	13.65
4	12.95	5.80	18.75	30.93	15.11	3.62	18.73	19.30
6	11.40	7.30	18.70	38.93	14.53	4.19	18.72	22.35
8	9.78	8.87	18.65	47.31	12.80	5.86	18.66	31.25
12	8.92	9.72	18.64	51.84	12.52	6.18	18.70	32.96
24	7.20	11.40	18.60	60.80	11.47	7.24	18.71	38.61
48	7.03	11.52	18.55	61.44	11.09	7.54	18.63	40.21
120	6.99	11.59	18.58	61.81	11.05	7.60	18.65	40.53

TABLE III

Account of oxygen rendered available (in m.e. [g.] during the hydrolysis of bromine in presence of charcoal.

Description of the sample. (1)	Oxygen as free CO ₂ formed during the reaction (2)	Oxygen evolved as CO ₂ . (3)	CO. (4)	H ₂ O. (5)	Total chemisorbed oxygen. (6)	Oxygen chemisorbed during the reaction with bromine. (7)	Total oxygen that can be accounted for (2+7). (8)	Amount of oxygen expected (equivalent to the amount of HBr produced). (9)
Before treatment with bromine.								
Sugar charcoal		13.46	10.06	13.89	37.41			
						47.02-37.41 =9.61		
After treatment with bromine.								
	2.06	23.12	9.98	13.92	47.02		11.67	11.82
Before treatment with bromine.								
Coconut shell charcoal		6.34	7.78	8.58	22.70			
						28.92-22.70 =6.22		
After treatment with bromine.								
	1.32	12.02	7.69	8.61	28.92		7.54	7.63

TABLE IV

Interaction of bromine water and evacuated samples of sugar charcoal.

Conc. of bromine water. (1)	Bromine added to 1 g. charcoal (250×N). (2)	Analysis of bromine water (in m.e.) after shaking.							
		Evacuated at 750°.				Evacuated at 1100°.			
		Bromine unchanged. (3)	HBr formed. (4)	Total amount of Br ₂ and HBr (3+4). (5)	Bromine 'fixed' by charcoal (2 to 5). (6)	Bromine unchanged. (7)	HBr formed. (8)	Total amount of Br ₂ and HBr. (9)	Bromine 'fixed' by charcoal. (10)
0.035 N	8.75 m.e.	4.00	0.25	4.25	4.50	3.90	0.20	4.10	4.65
0.055	13.75	8.82	0.28	9.10	4.65	8.80	0.20	9.00	4.75
0.075	18.75	13.90	0.30	14.20	4.65	14.05	0.20	14.25	4.80
0.095	23.75	18.85	0.30	19.15	4.60	18.98	0.22	19.20	4.85
0.115	28.75	23.76	0.26	24.02	4.73	23.01	0.24	24.15	4.90
0.130	33.50	27.52	0.30	27.82	4.68	27.72	0.25	27.97	4.83

TABLE V

Heat of 'fixation' of bromine by the 750°- and 1100°- evacuated samples of sugar charcoal.

Conc. of bromine soln.	Amount of bromine added (200×N).	Heat evolved during the fixation of bromine by charcoal.	Amount of bromine fixed by charcoal.	Heat of fixation of bromine (Kcal./mole).
750°-evacuated sample.				
0.024N	4.8 m.e.	84.99 cal.	8.18 m.e.	20.78
0.038	7.6	139.65	14.57	19.17
0.063	12.6	170.64	18.40	20.81
0.151	30.2	190.82	18.64	20.47
1100°-evacuated sample.				
0.026	5.2	8.08	7.98	20.07
0.054	10.8	100.75	10.25	19.66
0.093	18.6	132.27	13.12	20.16
0.112	22.4	172.28	16.55	20.62

DISCUSSION

It is seen (Table II) that there is a slow, though progressive, conversion of bromine into hydrobromic acid in presence of the original samples of sugar as well as coconut shell charcoals up to about 24 hours, after which a state of equilibrium appears to set in. The percentage conversion at any time is more in sugar charcoal than in coconut shell charcoal. This may be due to larger surface area of the sugar charcoal (Puri and Sharma, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1956, 15B, 178). The hydrobromic acid formed was mostly in solution; only a small amount was found to be adsorbed by the charcoal, which too could be recovered on washing with hot distilled water. The values recorded in Table II represent the total amounts of the acid formed. The results of blank experiments (without charcoal) under similar conditions showed neither any formation of hydrobromic acid nor any decrease in the concentration of bromine.

The conversion of bromine into hydrobromic acid, as reported in Table II, is presumably due to hydrolysis of the halogen brought about in the presence of charcoal. An equivalent amount of oxygen therefore must be taken up by the charcoal in some form. In order to verify this, the gaseous mixture above the reaction bottle as well as that evolved on degassing the treated charcoals at 1200° was analysed by an Orsat-Lunge gas analysis apparatus in the usual way. The results are recorded in Table III. The amount of the gases evolved on degassing the same charcoals before treatment with bromine water, expressed in the same units, are also included for comparison. A considerable amount of oxygen, rendered available during the reaction with bromine water, appears to be chemisorbed by the charcoal (col. 7) and it is evolved mostly as carbon dioxide (col. 3) on high-temperature evacuation. A much smaller amount of the oxygen gives rise to gaseous carbon dioxide (col. 2) which collects in the reaction vessel. The total oxygen that can be accounted for in these two forms (col. 8) is almost exactly equivalent to the amount of hydrobromic acid formed (col. 9).

This agreement confirms the view that bromine is hydrolysed in presence of charcoal. Further, as the entire amount of bromine added can be accounted for as hydrobromic acid formed and as bromine left unchanged (Table II), it is evident that none of it is taken up as such by these samples of charcoal.

The results obtained on shaking with bromine solutions of varying concentrations with 750°- and 1100°- degassed samples of sugar charcoal for 24 hours are recorded in Table IV. There is little or no formation of hydrobromic acid now. An appreciable fall in the concentration of bromine was, however, noticed in each case. Similar results were obtained with the degassed coconut shell charcoals. Evidently degassed charcoals, devoid of chemisorbed oxygen disposed as carbon dioxide (Table I), unlike the original samples, can 'fix' an appreciable amount of bromine. This bromine could not be recovered on repeated washings with water nor even on high-temperature evacuation of the charcoal at 1200°.

Incidentally, the amount of bromine fixed by 750°- as well as 1100°-degassed sugar charcoal is about the same and almost independent of the initial concentration of the bromine solution. The average value is approximately 4.61 m.e./g. sugar charcoal. The corresponding value for degassed coconut shell charcoals is 3.75 m.e./g. These are appreciably high values and amount to 36.86% and 30.6% on the weight of these charcoals respectively. The results of ultimate analysis of the treated charcoals gave almost identical values,

This large amount of bromine is very likely linked to some unsaturated sites created by the elimination of that part of chemisorbed oxygen which is evolved as carbon dioxide. The elimination of the rest of the oxygen, evolved as carbon monoxide and water, does not appear to cause any additional unsaturated sites because, although the 750°- and 1100°-evacuated samples differ appreciably in their oxygen of this form (Table I), there is no noticeable difference in the amounts of bromine 'fixed' by them. Such unsaturated sites are apparently absent in the original samples since these are incapable of 'fixing' any bromine. These can bring about, however, hydrolysis of bromine to a considerable extent, as already shown (Table II). Thus the nature of the reaction between charcoal and bromine in aqueous solution depends very largely on the nature of the charcoal surface.

The results of thermal measurements using bromine solutions of different concentrations with 750°- and 1100°-degassed charcoals are recorded in Table V. Contrary to the results reported in Table IV, the amount of bromine 'fixed' by charcoal is now seen to increase with the initial concentration of the solution and the cause is attributed to the duration of these experiments for one hour only. Whenever sufficient time was allowed for the attainment of the equilibrium, the amount of bromine 'fixed' was invariably about the same and independent of the concentration of the bromine solution used.

It is noteworthy that the heat of 'fixation' of bromine per mole is almost the same in each sample of charcoal, irrespective of the concentration of the solution used or of the amount of the reactants. The average value is seen to be about 20.24 Kcal./mole.

The heat of addition of bromine in ethylenic double bond has been found to be between 28 and 31 Kcal./mole (Lister, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 143; Mochulsky and Tobolsky, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1948, **40**, 2155). This heat refers to the reaction of bromine in the gaseous phase. By adding heat of condensation of bromine (7.50 Kcal./mole) and its heat of solution in potassium bromide (3.7 Kcal./mole, as determined by the authors in the concentration range used by them) to 20.24 Kcal., a value equal to 31.44 Kcal. is obtained, which is quite close to the value reported in literature. This agreement indicates that the bromine 'fixed' by degassed charcoal is taken up at some unsaturated sites.